

CLIMATE CHANGE: IS THERE A NEED FOR CLIMATE CHANGE EMERGENCY?

Dr. Badar Alam Iqbal

CLIMATE CHANGE: IS THERE A NEED FOR CLIMATE CHANGE EMERGENCY?

Dr. Badar Alam Iqbal

Editorial

Climate Change: Is There a Need for Climate Change Emergency?

Dr. Badar Alam Iqbal¹

Climate Change has remained one of the most vital and controversial issues at global forums in the 21st century. While it is generally accepted that climate change needs universal metrics, there is still no consensus on climate change practices among global economies worldwide (Stadelmann, Michaelowa, Butzengeiger-Geyer, & Köhler, 2011). Emerging economies target high growth rates and push their economies with industrial production, which, in turn, poses a climate change challenge. It has made the climate change issue for emerging economies a matter of policy (Jayanti & Gowda, 2014).

COVID-19 and Climate Change

The world today is reeling under the impact of COVID-19. It is expected that even when the pandemic ends or partially ends, the world will be faced with a new normal. COVID-19 will have implications on the economic, political, demographic, and social structures of emerging economies. Recent studies have suggested the impact of the pandemic on financial markets (Zhang, Hu, & Ji, 2020), central bank swap lines (Bahaj & Reis, 2020), and healthcare (Keesara, Jonas, & Schulman, 2020), and other dimensions. The pandemic has pushed for unprecedented social and economic changes that may cut both ways in emerging economies. The pandemic initially halted the digital progress in world but later governments started investing in it (Strielkowski, 2020; Georgiou, 2020).

Climate Change Impact

A recent study has found a correlation between climate indicators and the COVID-19 pandemic (Bashir, Ma, Komal, Bashir, Tan, & Bashir, 2020). It is being seen that the demand for energy by emerging economies is slowly reducing due to the ongoing pandemic. It has to be seen whether it will rise again or be sustainable in the near future. The global economic slowdown has already reduced energy consumption worldwide. The positive impacts of the pandemic on climate by way of clean air, lakes, reduced mobility, etc., is already apparent to people.

¹ Adjunct Professor, Economics and Finance, Monarch Business School, Switzerland
dr.badar@umonarch-email.ch

Adding Fuel to the Fire

The present conflict between Russia and Ukraine is adding fuel to the fire. It may prove to be a disaster to the global economy as well as emerging and developing economies. If the war continues, it will bear effects, implications, and consequences on the world economy. There is thus an urgent need for an action plan to tackle the environmental impacts of war on climate change.

Global Scenario

The 17th edition of the Climate Change Performance Index (CCPI), prepared by Germanwatch and Climate Action Network, is an eye-opener for people across the globe. All countries, whether developed or developing, must consider the findings of the CCPI on a war footing.

The CCPI is responsible for monitoring the climate mitigation progress and status of 60 countries plus 27 states of the European Union. The index has placed Denmark, Sweden, Morocco, and the United Kingdom (UK) on high ranking; their performances must be a lesson to countries around the world. However, what is most alarming is the fact that no country has been placed in the first three ranks of the index.

They have been left empty as no country has performed well enough across all parameters to secure an overall high ranking. On the other side, countries that are champions of the climate change cause, namely the United States (US), Russia, Australia, and South Korea, are finding themselves at the lowest rungs. India is placed at the tenth position, way ahead of China whose overall ranking is 37. The index also revealed that India benefits from its relatively lower per capita emissions.

Countries with Prime Responsibility

A long-time outstanding disagreement at the United Nations Climate Summits is whether and how the wealthiest countries, which are disproportionately responsible for the increasing trend in global warming to date, have failed to discharge their respective historical responsibility for meeting the ever-rising issue of climate change. These nations should compensate poorer countries for the damage caused by rising temperature. The most prosperous economies, especially the US, Canada, Japan, and the Western European countries, account for only 12 per cent of the world's total population but are responsible for 50 per cent of the total greenhouse gases generated from fossil fuels and industry for the last 170 years.

Silver Lining

The COVID-19 pandemic has positively impacted carbon emissions by reducing emissions due to industrial shutdown and limited human mobility. However, once the pandemic ends or the engine of industrial activity restarts, the issue of emissions will again pile up. While considering the abovementioned issues, this special issue was organised wherein contributors were asked to take a critical look at the trends and situation regarding climate change and suggest much-needed amicable solutions.

This special issue contains seven papers of divergent nature—in terms of topic, contents, and nature—which aim to cover different facets of the theme.

All seven papers have provided a critical look at the issues and suggested valuable inputs for planners and policymakers in their endeavour to tackle the alarming issue of climate change.

I am thankful to authors, reviewers, editorial board members, and the publisher of the journal; without their commitment, this special issue would not have been not successfully published. I hope that the content of this issue is value addition and will add significantly to the existing literature on the subject. I sincerely hope the readers will enjoy the papers.

References Data

- Bahaj, S., & Reis, R. (2020). Central bank swap lines during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Covid Economics*, 2. <http://personal.lse.ac.uk/reisr/papers/20-covicbswaps.pdf>
- Bashir, M. F., Ma, B., Komal, B., Bashir, M. A., Tan, D., & Bashir, M. (2020). Correlation between climate indicators and COVID-19 pandemic in New York, USA. *Science of the Total Environment*, 728(138835). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138835>
- Georgiou, M. (2020). Solidarity at the time of COVID-19: An (other) digital revolution. *Media@LSE*, 1–5. <http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/104157/>
- Jayanti, R. K., & Gowda, M. R. (2014). Sustainability dilemmas in emerging economies. *IIMB Management Review*, 26, 130–142. <https://repository.iimb.ac.in/handle/2074/11494>
- Kesara, S., Jonas, A., & Schulman, K. (2020). COVID-19 and health care's digital revolution. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 382(23), e82. <https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMp2005835>
- Stadelmann, M., Michaelowa, A., Butzengeiger-Geyer, S., & Köhler, M. (2011). Universal metrics to compare the effectiveness of climate change adaptation projects. In *Colorado Conference on Earth System Governance: Crossing Boundaries and Building Bridges*, May, 17–20.
- Strielkowski, W. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic and the digital revolution in academia and higher education. <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202004.0290/v1>
- Zhang, D., Hu, M., & Ji, Q. (2020). Financial markets under the global pandemic of COVID-19. *Finance Research Letters*, 36, 101528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2020.101528>

10-3-303, 3rd Floor, Serene Heights Building,
Humayun Nagar, Masab Tank, Hyderabad - 500 028
info@cdpp.co.in | www.cdpp.co.in